
IMPROVED PROCESSING PROCEDURE OF MELON SEEDS TO REDUCE THE OFFENSIVE ODOUR OF 'OGIRI'

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Abstract

This study was carried out to improve the existing processing procedure of melon seeds to reduce the offensive odour of "ogiri". Experimental research design was used to carry out the study. Ogiri produced by three methods (samples R, Y & I i.e. Researcher's, Yoruba and Igbo methods respectively) were subjected to proximate analysis and level of acceptability. Seven hedonic scales were used to determine acceptability of colour, appearance, flavour or taste, odour, texture and overall acceptability. The result indicated that, the three samples of ogiri had nutritional contents. Sample R has 13.42g of % crude protein and 7.45mg/100g of vitamin A, sample Y has 11.24g of % crude protein and 7.23mg /100g of vitamin A and sample I has 10.44g % crude protein and 6.73mg/100g of vitamin A. Result of the acceptability test shows that sample R was the most widely accepted. Based on these findings, it was recommended that there should be nutrition education to enlighten the populace about nutritional contents of ogiri and that the new method of preparation which reduced the offensive odour, was the most nutritious and most widely accepted.

Introduction

Man has known of the existence and uses of melons since the past four thousand years and today, a wide variety of melons are known to exist around the world (Agro Product, 2008). Thought to be originally from the Middle Eastern region, the melon seeds were transported to the Americas by Columbus and the Spanish explorers (www.tarladalal.com 2011; Agro Products, 2008). In India, these cooling and nutritious fruits are found in abundance during

the summer time. The melon seed is a refreshing and healthy food because it is lower in calories and has a high water content (www.tarladalai.com 2011; Agro Products, 2008).

Egusi refers to the seeds of a highly nutritious type of melon found widely in Africa called 'citrullus lanatus'. Egusi seeds are flat oval seeds with a tapering pointed end, milky to white in colour, very rich in protein. A special type of highly nutritious plant oil (healthy and cholesterol free) is made from the seeds. It is used in preparing the popular egusi soup, in making cakes and other fruit snacks. (www.africanfoods.co.uk.2011).

It is popularly used in soups in West and Central Africa. It is also called melon, 'agushi' or 'guna shanu' (Hausa), ikpoghiri (Itsekiri), neri niri (Ghanians) or ibara (Congolese). They have a very long shelf life and are quite versatile in the ranges of uses they can be put into both in human and livestock feeding (www.africanfoods.co.uk.2011). They grow on dry land and have a high brown shell or husk covering the whitish seed. They look like the pumpkin seed in appearance. It is not uncommon to find families sitting around a tray full of this seed removing husk from it.

Egusi is very high in nutritional value. It is made up of 30 to 40 percent protein, and about the same proportion of oil. 78 percent of the fat is unsaturated fatty acid, which is protective to the heart. It contains alpha-tocopherol a component of Vitamin E that helps in maintaining smooth young skin and good fertility. It also contains palmitic, stearic, linoleic and oleic acids important in protecting the heart too and very small amount of carbohydrate and calcium (www.africanfoods.co.uk,2011). If you are new to African foods, and looking for one recipe or African food item to taste, this soup sewed with pounded yam is a must eat.

Melon harvested when matured has high sugar content (about 14g in a serving size of 177.0g of melon seeds (nutritiondata.self.com, 2012; caloriecount.about.com, 2012)) and so the flesh of the fruit begins to soften at this stage. They are then cut into equal halves to fasten the decaying process, then packed together and kept under shady trees until the internal cavity decays, leaving the seeds afloat in the endosperm pods. The seeds are

then collected, washed and dried. The amount of yield from a particular cultivation depends on the soil fertility, the specie of the plant and the amount of rainfall. However, a good yield of about 20-60kg of dried seeds per hectare would be considered relatively satisfactory (Bankole, Osho, Joda & Enikuomihin, 2005).

The importance of melon seeds cannot be overemphasized. Some of the products from the melon seed such as salad oil, vegetable oil and margarine are consumed for nutritional purpose (Izuagie, 2008). Melon seeds are used directly as food after being processed.

They are prepared and consumed as 'Egusi' soup, melon ball, snacks (e.g. roasted melon seeds) and ogiri (fermented condiment) (Fayemi, 1999). The oil extracted from the seeds is used for edible purposes such as salad oil, cooking oil and margarine while the residual cake is fried and consumed as snacks e.g. robon (Fayemi, 1999). Also the oil and fat are important sources of energy and they act as carriers for fat and vitamins. Hence, making melon vital in the human diet (Bankole, 2003).

Melon seeds are processed and fermented to provide ogiri which is a popular proteineous food condiment used habitually in enhancing the aroma and flavour of many traditional dishes (Bankole, 2003). Ogiri has been recorded to date back to as early as the melon seed itself and has since then remained favoured by its consumers not only in Nigeria but also in West Africa as a whole.

In Africa, where protein-calorie malnutrition is a major problem, the socio-economic and nutritional importance of soup and sauces cannot be over emphasized. Proteineous condiments like Ogiri and Iru contribute a good portion of vegetable protein to soups even though they are used in small quantities. They also promote the mineral contents of these traditional soups. These food flavouring condiments are prepared by traditional method of uncontrolled solid substrate fermentation. This process results in extensive hydrolysis of the protein and carbohydrate components and this gives rise to the production of offensive odour. Apart from increasing the anti-nutritional factors, fermentation markedly improves the digestibility, nutritive value and flavours of raw seeds (Bankole, 2003).

Fermented melon seeds (Ogiri) acts as a condiment used in the preparation of stew and soup food such as 'Ikokore' (cultural food in Ijebu made from water yam), vegetable melon soup, Okro or cocorum (Ewedu) and so on. It adds flavour to the food thereby making it pleasant to taste. As investigated by nutritionalists, it contains fifteen essential amino acids (Fayemi, 1999).

One major problem that besets melon seeds is that they deteriorate quickly in storage due to fungal infection. The effects of fungal attacks on melon seeds include decrease in the peroxide value, reduction in seed germination and mycotoxin production. Meanwhile, seeds that are meant for consumption should not exhibit any of these properties. Rapid drying to lower the moisture content is often emphasized.

Various dehydration methods can be used to reduce the moisture content of melon seeds and one of such methods is the traditional sun drying process where seeds are spread on floor or mat and exposed to air to dry. But because of conditions of high ambient relative humidity, particularly during the period of the first harvesting season (July to September) sun drying often results in unnecessary extension of drying periods which may affect the quality of the seeds. Bankole, et al (2005) also reported that smoking and oven drying significantly reduced the moisture content of melon seeds without altering the physical and chemical attributes of the seeds and it also resulted in improved storability of the seeds. Thus making those methods considerable for the first harvesting season, that is (July-August) in the rainforest belt of West Africa when sun drying often proves very difficult due to humid weather conditions.

Most traditionally fermented condiments are processed similarly and these methods include parboiling, dehulling, washing, boiling, packaging into leaves and fermentation.

Parboiling: The raw seeds are packed into a pot after initial screening of dirt in the seeds and then boiled to soften the hard testa. The aim of the operation is to soften the hull and bloat the seeds for easy separation from its cotyledon. Therefore the operation can extend till the hull is removable. Parboiling however removes some anti-nutritional factors of oil seeds.

Dehulling: This is basically the removal of outer coat called hull from seeds cotyledon. This process is normally done traditionally by manual operation. Thumb pressure is applied to the seeds to remove the hull or they may be rubbed between the palms of the hand to remove the hull.

Washing: After the dehulling operation, they are then washed with clean water to remove any visible dirt.

Boiling: The seeds are boiled in water *until* they become soft when felt with thumb.

Packaging into Leaves: At this stage the half processed seeds are mediumly proportioned and packaged into leaves. The choice of leaves differs depending on the locality of the production plant. However, common ones are banana leaves.

Fermentation: The already wrapped products are packed together and left to ferment at normal room temperature for 3-5 days.

Mashing: Melon is mashed manually using a pestle and a mortar to break the seeds into pieces.

Table 1 describes the Yoruba traditional method of producing ogiri

TABLE 1: TRADITIONAL PRODUCTION OF OGIRI (YORUBA METHOD)

Boiling	Draining	Fermentation	Pounding
Egusi (melon) is put into pot and boiled usually for 10-16 hours or until very soft.	The seed are then drained and conditioned then packed into leaves	Fermentation is usually 3-4 days at room temperature of about 30°C	The characteristic pasty nature is achieved for large quantities.

Source: (Oyedepo, 2000)

Traditional Production of Ogiri (Igbo Method)

'Ogiri-Igbo is processed the same way as Ogiri Yoruba but, fermentation is by microorganism at pH 6.5 to 8 and temperature between 31 and 45°C. There is an addition of about 2gm of charcoal that is, activated carbon which helps in the removal of odour and colour.

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Below is the flow chart for local production of ogiri from melon seed.

Flow Chart for Local Production of Ogiri Condiment from Melon Seed

Raw Melon Seed

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Deshelling

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Sorting

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Washing

↓
Boiling (6 hours)

↓
Dehulling

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Rinsing

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Washing

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Draining

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Washing

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Conditioning (5-7 hours at room temp.)

Ogiri-Igbo Source: (Oyedepo, 2000)

Laboratory Production of Ogiri Igbo

The common knowledge of the production of Ogiri traditionally has helped researchers and scientists to be able to manipulate the production condition in the laboratory. Bacteria are the most predominant micro organisms involved in the fermentation of food condiment. The pH ranges from 6.5-8, and temperature is between 31 and 45°C. There was also improvement on the mineral and vitamin profile of the seed especially vitamin C as indicated in the flow chat (Oyedepo, 2000).

Flow Chart showing the Laboratory processing of 'Ogiri-Igbo'

Sources: (Oyedepo, 2000)

Bearing in mind the nutritive value of the local condiment, it is important to produce it in a way that its offensive odour will be reduced and the shelf life will be improved upon. The globalization and liberation of Nigerian economy has brought about the introduction of foreign, high technological productions especially processed products. This has however, radically changed the Nigerian food culture to a mixed grill of foreign and local dishes. These conditions: a very short shelf life, stickiness, putrid characteristic odour and an objectionably packaging material have all hindered the acceptability and use of ogiri.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to improve the existing processing procedure of melon seed to reduce the offensive odour of Ogiri.

Specific Objectives of the Study

- To determine the nutritional content of Ogiri produced through

three different methods.

- To determine the contribution of Ogiri to the Recommended Dietary Allowance.
- To determine the level of acceptability of Ogiri produced by the three different methods.

Research Questions

- i. What is the nutritional content of Ogiri produced by three different methods?
- ii. What is the contribution of Ogiri to the Recommended Dietary Allowance?
- iii. What is the level of acceptability of Ogiri produced by the three different methods?

Materials and Methods

Ogiri was prepared by three methods. These are: the Researcher's method (which will hence forth be referred to as sample R), Yoruba method (sample Y) and Igbo method (sample I).

Design of the Study

Experimental research design was used to carry out this study. Experimental research is used to establish cause and effect relationships. It is the most powerful and valid design which can be used to identify confidently the cause of any given effect. It also involves one or more independent variables which are manipulated by the Researcher under controlled condition and its effect observed (Nworgu, 2006).

Area of the Study

This study was carried out in the Food and Nutrition laboratory of the Department of Home Economics, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. Ondo town is located in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA). OWLGA is one of the eighteen Local Government Areas in Ondo State.

Description of Materials

The ingredients used for preparing the three samples of ogiri were purchased from Igele market in Ondo, Ondo state, Nigeria.

Igele market is one of the six markets in OWLGA. It is the biggest of the six markets and all goods are available for sale there. Preparations of the three samples were carried out in the Food and Nutrition laboratory of the Department of Home Economics, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo. The three samples were subjected to proximate analysis at the Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T) Ibadan. The three samples of ogiri were analyzed for their crude protein and vitamin A content.

Crude protein in the sample were determined by the routine semi-micro kjeldahl procedure/technique. Vitamin A was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

PREPARATION OF THE THREE SAMPLES

SAMPLE R (Researcher's Method)

INGREDIENTS: 2cups of melon seed, water, scent leaves, sack, covered pot, granulated sugar, salt, oven, banana leaves.

Table 2 shows the Researcher's method of preparing ogiri

TABLE 2: METHOD OF PREPARATION

Boiling	Draining	Fermentation	Dehydration
2 cups of melon seeds were washed and put in a covered pot, scent leaves were also washed and added, the mixture were boiled until very soft.	The seeds were drained and the scent leaves were removed. The seeds were packed immediately into a sack. The sack was put into a pot already smeared with granulated sugar and covered.	Fermentation was allowed to take place for 3 days (at room temperature). On the third day it was pounded into a paste. Salt was added to it immediately and it was mixed thoroughly.	Paste were wrapped with banana leaves and put inside the oven to remove the water for 2 days.

SAMPLE Y (Yoruba Method)

INGREDIENTS

2 cups of melon seeds, water, akoko leaves, sack, covered pot, salt, smoker, banana leaves

Table 3 shows the Yoruba's method of preparing ogiri

TABLE 3: METHOD OF PREPARATION

Boiling	Draining	Fermentation	Dehydration
2 cups of melon seeds were washed and put in a covered pot, Akoko leaves were also washed and added. The mixtures were boiled until very soft.	The seeds were drained and Akoko leaves were removed. The seeds were allowed to cool and packed into a sack. The sacks were put inside a covered pot.	Fermentation was allowed to take place for 4 days (at room temperature). On the fourth day it was pounded into paste and wrapped with banana and Akoko leaves for the second fermentation which took place for 3 days.	Pastes were smoked for 2 days and ready for consumption.

SAMPLE I (Igbo Method)

INGREDIENTS

2 cups of melon seeds, water, Akoko leaves, sack, covered pot, salt, banana leaves.

Table 4 shows Igbo's method of preparing ogiri

TABLE 4: METHOD OF PREPARATION

Boiling	Draining	Fermentation	Dehydration
2 cups of melon seeds were washed and put in a covered pot, Akoko leaves were also washed and added. The mixtures were boiled until very soft.	The seeds were drained and Akoko leaves were removed. The seeds were allowed to cool and packed into a sack. The sacks were put inside a pot and covered.	Fermentation was allowed to take place for 3 days (at room temperature). On the third day it was pounded into paste and charcoal was added and wrapped with banana leaves for the second fermentation which took place for 3 days.	Pastes were sun dried for 2 days and ready for consumption.

Acceptability

The three samples were tested for their levels of acceptability by a panel of eighteen judges, comprising: eight senior staff members (3 females and 5 males), three Junior Staff members (2 females and 1 male) and seven students (5 females and 2 males) all of Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo.

Each of the three samples was used in turns to prepare okro soups with pounded yam. Each panelist was served with one wrap of pounded yam with the 3 samples of soup attached to each. The acceptability forms given to the panelists were designed to indicate their choices of number from (1-7). That is, dislike very much, dislike moderately, dislike slightly, intermediate, like slightly, like moderately and like very much, about their options on colour appearance, flavour/taste, odour, texture and overall acceptability.

Results and Discussions

Data Analysis

These three samples (R, Y, I) were each subjected to two rounds of analysis to determine their crude protein and vitamin A content.

Table 5 represents the calculated average percentage mean values of the crude protein of each of the three samples analyzed by IAR&T Ibadan.

TABLE 5: CRUDE PROTEIN

S/N	Samples Code	%Crude Protein		Average % Crude Protein
		Test 1	Test 2	
01	Sample R (Researchers method).	13.40	13.43	$\frac{13.40+13.43}{2}$ = 13.42g
02	Sample Y (Yoruba method).	11.25	11.23	$\frac{11.25+11.23}{2}$ = 11.24g
03	Sample I (Igbo method).	10.17	10.71	$\frac{10.17+10.71}{2}$ = 10.44g

According to table 5, the three samples contained meaningful values of crude protein which were only slightly different from each other. Sample R had the highest percentage of crude protein which was 13.42g; sample Y 11.24g and Sample I had the lowest percentage of 10.44g. From table 5, sample R had the highest percentage of crude protein.

TABLE 6: VITAMIN A CONTENT OF SAMPLES

S/N	Samples Code	Vitamin A (mg/100g)		Average Vitamin (mg/100g)
		Test 1	Test 2	
01	Sample R (Researchers method).	7.48	7.43	$\frac{7.48+7.43}{2}$ = 7.45mg/100g
02	Sample Y (Yoruba method).	7.24	7.21	$\frac{7.24+7.21}{2}$ = 7.23mg/100g
03	Sample I (Igbo method).	6.74	6.72	$\frac{6.74+6.72}{2}$ = 6.73mg/100g

According to table 6, the three samples contained meaningful value of vitamin A content which were similar in values. Sample R had the highest value of 7.45mg/100g, sample Y had 7.23mg/100g and sample I had 6.73mg/100g. From table 6, sample R also had the highest vitamin A content.

TABLE 7: TABLE SHOWING DISLIKE, INTERMEDIATE AND LIKE OF SAMPLE R

Variables	Frequency of Dislike	Frequency of Intermediate	Frequency of Like
Colour Appearance	0	0	20
Flavour/Tastes	0	2	18
Odour	0	1	19
Texture	0	2	18
Overall Acceptability	0	1	10
	0%	6%	94%

According to table 7, sample R was highly accepted for colour, odour, flavour, texture, and overall acceptability. Levels of dislike was 0%, intermediate was 6% and level of like was 94%.

TABLE 8: TABLE SHOWING DISLIKE, INTERMEDIATE AND LIKE OF SAMPLE R

Variables	Frequency of Dislike	Frequency of Intermediate	Frequency of Like
Colour Appearance	2	2	16
Flavour/Tastes	1	3	16
Odour	1	2	17
Texture	1	3	16
Overall Acceptability	3	0	17
	8%	10%	82%

According to table 8, sample Y was slightly accepted for Colour, Flavour, Odour, Texture and Overall Acceptability. Level of dislike was 8% intermediate 10% and like was 82%.

TABLE 9: TABLE SHOWING DISLIKE, INTERMEDIATE AND LIKE OF SAMPLE R

Variables	Frequency of Dislike	Frequency of Intermediate	Frequency of Like
Colour Appearance	4	1	15
Flavour/Tastes	1	2	17
Odour	5	0	15
Texture	0	1	19
Overall Acceptability	1	0	19
	11%	4%	85%

According to table 9, sample I was moderately accepted for colour, flavour, odour, texture and overall acceptability. Level of dislike was 11%, intermediate was 4% and like was 85%.

Discussion of the Result

It was observed from the findings that ogiri by the three different methods contained appreciable amounts of vitamin A and percentage crude protein. According to table 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 sample R showed 13.42g of crude protein which might have been due to the scent leaves added. It also showed appreciable amount of vitamin A (7.45mg/100g) and the highest level of acceptability (94%). Samples Y and I showed 11.24g and 10.44g of crude protein respectively. The level of acceptability for both samples (Y and I) were 82% and 85% respectively while vitamin A values reflected 7.23mg/100g and 6.73mg/100g respectively which could be attributed to the added Akoko leaves.

The value above, especially for crude protein is in line with reports of Izuagie, 2008; that melon seed has high nutritional value since it contains 30-40% protein and about same proportion of oil.

This shows that Ogiri especially sample R (Researchers method) will assist in meeting the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) of vitamin A and protein. Whitney and Rolfes, (2008) reported that vitamin A requirement for infants between 0-3years was 300µg/day while crude protein was 13g/day. It will supply the needed crude protein and vitamin A requirement for infants and adult including pregnant women and lactating mothers.

Ogiri produced by the researcher's method will assist in meeting (RDA) for vitamin A and crude protein in the absence of other proteineous and vitamin A rich foods, if included in the diet of all age groups of humans especially the infants and children.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary

This research was carried out to enlighten the society about the nutritive value of ogiri produced by two tribes (Yoruba, Igbo) and Researcher's method. It was also directed at reducing the characteristic odour associated with the produce. Most people believed that ogiri producers are unhygienic. Therefore this research exposed them to produce ogiri of their own choice in a more hygienic manner and environment. The nutritional content of the three samples show good quality, however, sample R was the most nutritious and mostly accepted. Although sample Y and I reflected good nutritional quality, both samples were unable to meet the odourless characteristic of sample R.

Conclusion

This research *work* has been able to produce ogiri with reduced offensive odour and in an hygienic environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this project, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Awareness (through work shop, seminar and public lectures) should be created on:

- (a) The new method of producing ogiri to reduce the offensive odour associated with it.
 - (b) The nutritional quality of ogiri especially vitamin A and crude protein contents and that if ogiri is included in people's diet it will assist in meeting Recommended Dietary Allowance of vitamin A and crude protein.
 - (c) That Ogiri can be produced in hygienic environment.
2. (a) Studies should be conducted to find out if ogiri is produced by the third major tribe in Nigeria i.e Hausa.
(b) If it is not, it should be introduced to them.
 3. Further Studies should be conducted on the fat, other Vitamins and minerals present in the new method of producing ogiri.

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